

The Intimacy of STEM Education among the Secondary School Teachers and Administrators of Public Sector Schools of District Quetta, Balochistan : An ambition in shaping the STEM Image in District Quetta

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Abstract

Over the past decade, there has been an intensified emphasis on STEM education to correspond with the goals of 21st-century education. This study was conducted to gauge the intimacy and existing status of STEM education among the public sector secondary school teachers and institutions of district Quetta. It also highlights the teaching strategies employed by these teachers and their cohesiveness with the strategies of STEM education for the feasible implementation of STEM, and it also helps in the development of intimacy among these teachers. In order to achieve the objectives, quantitative methodology was used. In Quetta there has 134 public secondary schools (81 for girls and 53 for boys) with a total teaching deployed staff of 737 (405 male and 332 female). By using stratified random sampling, 70 girls' schools and 48 boys' schools were selected. By considering Krejcie and Morgan Table, a sample of 248 was determined and uniformly distributed between male and female teachers. Data were collected through a self-developed questionnaire, and analyzed by using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages). The results revealed that the intimacy of STEM education was generally low, and the existing status of STEM education was also not satisfactory. Furthermore, the teaching strategies employed by the teachers are not in line with the principles of STEM education. The study determines that the training programmes related to STEM should be incorporated in the teachers' trainings. Moreover, adequate laboratory facilities and availability of digital tools should be ensured for the successful transition from traditional methods of teaching to the market-advocated approaches.

Keywords: STEM Education, Public Sector Schools, Intimacy, Secondary School Teachers, Administrators.

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